

August 19, 2014

Dear Mrs Quinn,
Dear Mr Morrison,
Dear Mr Williams,
Dear Mr Arbyn,

We have read the protocol for the Cochrane review “Prophylactic Vaccination Against human papillomaviruses to prevent prevention cervical cancer and Its Precursors”, led by Marc Arbyn, Andrew Bryant, Pierre Martin-Hirsch PL, Lan Xu, Cindy Simoens and Lauri Markowitz. (CD009069 http://summaries.cochrane.org/CD009069/GYNAECA_prophylactic-vaccination-against-human-papillomaviruses-to-prevent-cervical-cancer-and-its-precursors and CD009069.pdf) with great interest.

We are pleased to see that this protocol addresses many important issues related to HPV vaccines. However, we believe that some points of clarification and some changes are necessary. Attached to this e-mail is a document containing our detailed comments.

We thank you in advance for taking our remarks and our suggestions for modifications of the protocol into consideration and hope to see these acted upon.

If you have any questions or seek further clarification, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Sincerely yours,

Catherine Riva
Journaliste indépendante
Rümikerstrasse 112
CH-8409 Wintetrhur

Dr Jean-Pierre Spinosa
Gynécologue-obstétricien
Rue des Terreaux 2
CH – 1003 Lausanne

Abby Lippman
PhD, Professor Emerita
Department of Epidemiology, Biostatistics. and Occupational Health
McGill University
Montréal, Québec

Neil Arya
BASc MD CCFP FCFP D. Litt
Adjunct Professor Environmental Studies University of Waterloo
Assistant Clinical Professor Family Medicine McMaster University

Pierre Biron
Professeur honoraire
Faculté de médecine
Université de Montréal
Canada 3

Geneviève Rail

Ph.D. Concordia University and CIHR recipient of a research grant on HPV vaccination (2012-2015)

Lyba Spring

Sexual Health Education and Consulting Services

414 Rushton Rd.

Toronto, Ontario

M6C 2Y3

Anne Taillefer B.SC., M.A.

Sociologue de la santé

Université du Québec à Montréal

Fernand Turcotte, MD. MPH. FRCPC

Professeur émérite de santé publique,

Université Laval

Québec, Canada